

**EFFECT OF PRIVATISATION AND COLLEGE AUTONOMY ON
QUALITY IN HIGHER EDUCATION :
AS PERCEIVED BY TEACHERS**

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ABSTRACT

The objectives of the study were to investigate i) the independent effect of privatisation on quality in higher education in terms of teachers' perception; ii) the independent effect of college autonomy on quality in higher education in terms of teachers' perception, and iii) the interaction effect of privatisation and college autonomy on quality in higher education in terms of teachers' perception relating to their satisfaction with quality of teaching, research activities, extension services, examination, curriculum, co-curricular activities, job satisfaction, students' support services, infrastructural facilities and educational climate. A sample of 120 teachers 30 each from government autonomous colleges, private autonomous colleges, government non-autonomous colleges and private non-autonomous colleges were selected randomly using multi stage sampling technique. The Satisfaction Scale for Teachers was developed by the investigator was used to collect data. The "f" test used to analyze data revealed that i) quality of higher education in government colleges was better than the quality of higher education in private colleges; ii) quality of higher education in autonomous was better than the quality of higher education in non-autonomous colleges, and iii) there found interaction effect of privatization and college autonomy on quality in higher education as perceived by teachers relating to their satisfaction with different dimensions of quality in higher education.

Key words: Privatisation, College Autonomy, Quality, Higher Education

1. Introduction :

A combination of unprecedented demand for access to higher education and the inability or unwillingness of governments to provide the necessary support has brought privatisation of higher education to the forefront. Across the globe, Privatisation of higher education is one of the most dynamic and fastest-growing segments of postsecondary education at the turn of the 21st century, worldwide-expanding rapidly in almost all parts of the world (Albatch, 2005) There has also been a growing demand for freedom and autonomy to higher educational institutions, for which Government of India has granted college autonomy to government and private colleges in the country with an objective to ensure quality in higher education. Autonomous colleges have academic freedom prescribe its own rules for admission, to frame their own curriculum and syllabi, admit students

by conducting entrance examinations, innovate and experiment with new methods and strategies for transacting curriculum, conduct examination and publish results, and award degrees to the students.

2. Rationale Of The Study :

Customer's satisfaction as the determining factor of assessing quality of goods and services has been recognized widely all over the globe. Goods and services if meets, exceeds and delights customers' needs expectations are judged having quality as it is evident from the definitions of quality postulated by Downey (1992) and Deming (1993). The teachers are the internal stakeholders of higher education. These Stakeholders, as described by Middlehurst (1992), have legitimate authority to communicate their views because of their close proximity to the system.

A retrospective analysis of the studies conducted

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by researchers on effectiveness of privatisation on quality in higher education has shown that most of the studies investigated status, growth, functioning and movement of private higher education institution with regards to evolution (Mabizela, 2002), trends and realities (Albatch, 2005), international trends (Gupta, 2005), academicians' perception (Nicolescu, 2007), role (Azad and Chandra, 2008; Tiwari et al., 2013; Shankar, 2016; Sudarshan and Subramanian, 2016), growth (Sawahel, 2011; Desiderio and Lechuga, 2012; Angam, 2015), issues (Okunola and Oladipo, 2012; Singh, 2015; Gregorutti et al., 2016), needs (Shammi, 2012; Baweja, 2017), movement (Varghese, 2012), expansion (Mwebi and Simatwa, 2013), functioning (Parashar, 2013), and attitude of college students (Mirza and Nisa, 2020) towards privatisation of higher education. Further, a retrospective analysis of the studies conducted by researchers on effectiveness of college autonomy on quality in higher education revealed that most of the studies investigated autonomy status (Al-Zyoud, 2001; Rao 2015; Margaret and Kavitha, 2018; Sharma and Singh, 2018) problems (Tilak, 2004), efficacy (Kapur 1993), financing (Dwibedi, 2006; Mueed et al. 2013) and functioning (Mathew and Patrick, 2016) of autonomous colleges. A critical examination of studies conducted so far on effectiveness of college autonomy on higher education revealed that a little study is available with regard to the impact of college autonomy on quality in higher education except studies conducted by Mohanty (2005) and Barik (2013). Mohanty's study compared the satisfaction of students and teachers with some structural and functional aspects of higher education and Barik (2013) studied perception of students, teachers, parents and Principals with regards to impact of college autonomy on quality in higher education

3. Research Gap :

From above analysis, it was revealed that not a single study has been conducted to assess both independent and interaction effects of privatisation and college autonomy on quality in higher education in terms of satisfaction of teachers with regard to different dimensions of higher education. Therefore, there needs empirical research to evaluate both independent and

interaction effects of privatisation and college autonomy on quality in higher education as perceived by teachers, so the findings would be benefitted for improvement of quality in higher education. For which the study has been undertaken.

4. Objectives :

- (i) To study the independent effect of privatisation on quality in higher education in terms of teachers' perception.
- (ii) To study the independent effect of college autonomy on quality in higher education in terms of teachers' perception.
- (iii) To study the interaction effect of privatisation and college autonomy on quality in higher education in terms of teachers' perception.

5. Hypotheses :

- (I) There exists significant independent effect of privatisation on quality in higher education in terms of teachers' perception.
- (ii) There exists significant independent effect of college autonomy on quality in higher education in terms of teachers' perception.
- (iii) There exists significant interaction effect of privatisation and college autonomy on quality in higher education in terms of teachers' perception.

6. Methodology Of The Study

6.1 Design:

The perception of teachers working in government colleges with private colleges and autonomous colleges with non-autonomous colleges with regard to different dimensions of higher education have been compared using causal-comparative method and ex-post facto research design.

6.2 Sample:

A sample of 120 teachers 30 each from government autonomous colleges, private autonomous colleges, government non-autonomous colleges and private non-autonomous colleges were selected randomly using multi stage sampling technique

6.3 Tools:

The Satisfaction Scale for Teachers developed by the investigator was used for collection of data. It was a five point scale that consisted of 60 items to assess

teachers' perception relating to their satisfaction with ten dimensions of higher education such as quality of teaching, research activities, extension services, examination, curriculum, co-curricular activities, job satisfaction, students' support services, infrastructural facilities and educational climate. The content validity of the scale was ascertained by experts' judgment and the reliability co-efficient of the scale was .93.

7.the Results :

7.1 Effect of Privatisation on Quality in Higher Education in terms of Teachers' Satisfaction:

By collapsing college autonomy, as can be seen in Table 1, there found out independent effect of privatisation on quality in higher education as perceived by teachers relating to their satisfaction with different dimensions of higher education ($F=29.18$; $df=1$; $P<.01$). The mean score of teachers working in government colleges on satisfaction scale was better than mean score of teachers working in private colleges ($M=210.9>M=188.88$).

TABLE -1
Summary of "F" values for Effect of Privatisation and College Autonomy on Quality in Higher Education relating to Teachers' Satisfaction (N=120)

Sources of variance	Degree of freedom (df)	Sum of Squares (SS)	Mean Square (MS)	'F' values	Level of Significance
Privatisation	1	14542.01	14542.01	29.18	0.01
Colleges Autonomy	1	12958.41	12958.41	26.00	0.01
Interaction	1	3774.41	3774.41	7.57	0.01
Within	116	57818.77	498.44		

Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that there exists no independent effect of privatisation on quality in higher education as perceived by teachers relating to their satisfaction was rejected in favour of research hypothesis.

7.2 Effect of College Autonomy on Quality in Higher Education in terms of Teachers' Satisfaction

By collapsing privatisation, as can be seen in Table. 1, there found out independent effect of college autonomy on quality in higher education as perceived by teachers relating to their satisfaction with different dimensions of quality in higher education. ($F=26.00$; $df=1$; $P<.01$).

Further, mean score of teachers working in autonomous colleges on satisfaction scale was better than mean score of teachers working in non-autonomous colleges ($M=210.28>M=189.5$). Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that there exists no independent effect of college autonomy on quality in higher education as

perceived by teachers relating to their satisfaction was rejected in favour of research hypothesis.

7.3 Interaction effect of Privatisation and College Autonomy on Quality in Higher Education in terms of Teachers' Satisfaction

Table.2 shows that there was interaction effect of privatisation and college autonomy on quality in higher education as perceived by teachers relating to their satisfaction ($F=7.57$; $df=1$; $P<.01$).

Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that there exists no interaction effect of privatisation and college autonomy on quality in higher education as perceived by teachers relating to their satisfaction was rejected in favour of research hypothesis.

Table.2 showing multiple comparisons of different groups for interaction effect of privatisation and college autonomy on quality in higher education using Scheffe method revealed a significance of difference between

quality of higher education in government autonomous colleges and private autonomous colleges ($F=10.55$; $df=116$; $P<.01$) in favour of government autonomous colleges ($M=226.9>M=193.67$). Further, it was also found out significance of difference between quality of higher education in government autonomous colleges and government non-autonomous colleges ($F=9.78$; df

$=116$; $P<.01$) in favour of government autonomous colleges ($M=226.9>M=194.9$); government autonomous colleges and private non-autonomous colleges ($F=17.50$; $df=116$; $P<.01$) in favour of government autonomous colleges ($M=226.9>M=184.1$) as perceived by teachers relating to their satisfaction with different dimensions of quality in higher education.

TABLE-2
'F' values obtained by the Scheffe Method for multiple comparisons of Quality in Higher Education relating to Teachers' Satisfaction (N=120)

Groups	Mean	'F' Values	Level of Significance
Govt. Auto. Colleges Vs Pvt. Auto. Colleges	226.9 193.67	10.55	0.01
Govt. Auto. Colleges Vs Govt. Non-auto. Colleges	226.9 194.9	9.78	0.01
Govt. Auto. Colleges Vs Pvt. Non-auto. Colleges	226.9 184.1	17.50	0.01
Pvt. Auto. Colleges Vs Govt. Non-auto. Colleges	193.67 194.9	0.01	NS
Pvt. Auto. Colleges Vs Pvt. Non-auto. Colleges	193.67 184.1	0.87	NS
Govt. Non-auto. Colleges Vs Pvt. Non-auto. Colleges	194.9 184.1	1.11	NS

Whereas there found out no significance of difference between quality of higher education in private autonomous colleges and government non-autonomous colleges ($F=0.01$; $df=116$; $P>.01$); private autonomous colleges and private non-autonomous colleges ($F=0.87$; $df=116$; $P>.01$); and government non-autonomous colleges and private non-autonomous colleges ($F=1.11$; $df=116$; $P>.01$) as perceived by teachers relating to their satisfaction with different dimensions of quality in higher education.

From above analysis the findings emerged were (i) quality of higher education in government

autonomous colleges was better than quality of higher education in private autonomous colleges; (ii) quality of higher education in government autonomous colleges was better than quality of higher education in government non- autonomous colleges; (iii) quality of higher education in government autonomous colleges was better than quality of higher education in private non-autonomous colleges; (iv) quality of higher education in private autonomous colleges and government non-autonomous colleges was on similar line; (v) quality of higher education in private autonomous colleges and private non-autonomous colleges was on similar line; and

(vi) quality of higher education in government non-autonomous colleges and private non-autonomous colleges was on similar line as perceived by teachers relating to their satisfaction with different dimensions of quality of higher education.

1. Major Findings :

- 1) There was significant independent effect of privatization on quality in higher education as perceived by teachers relating to their satisfaction. It can be concluded that quality of higher education in government colleges was better than the quality of higher education in private colleges.
- 2) There was significant independent effect of college autonomy on quality of higher education as perceived by teachers relating to their satisfaction. It can be concluded that quality of higher education in autonomous colleges was better than the quality of higher education in non-autonomous colleges.
- 3) There was interaction effect of privatisation and college autonomy on quality in higher education in terms of teachers' perception. (i) quality of higher education in government autonomous colleges was better than the quality of higher education in private autonomous colleges; (ii) quality of higher education in government autonomous colleges was better than the quality of higher education in government non- autonomous colleges; (iii) quality of higher education in government autonomous colleges was better than the quality of higher education in private non-autonomous colleges; (iv) quality of higher education in private autonomous colleges was better than the quality of higher education in private non-autonomous colleges; (v) quality of higher education in government non-autonomous colleges was better than quality of higher education in private non-autonomous; and (vi) quality of higher education in private autonomous colleges and government non-autonomous colleges was on similar line as perceived by teachers relating to their satisfaction with different dimensions of quality of higher education.

2. Conclusion :

The present study concludes with the establishment of an empirically verified proposition that college autonomy has positive effect on quality in higher education. The study concludes with such generalizations as i) there is an independent effect of privatisation on quality in higher education as such quality of higher education in government colleges is better than quality of higher education in private colleges as perceived teachers; ii) there is an independent effect of college autonomy on quality in higher education as such quality of higher education in autonomous colleges is better than the quality of higher education in non-autonomous colleges as perceived teachers; and iii) there is an interaction effect of privatisation and college autonomy on quality in higher education as perceived by teachers relating to their satisfaction with different dimensions of higher education.

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